

Morphological and electrical studies of Graphite nanostructures and its biological applications

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Man has created several artificial forms of carbon some of these are: synthetic graphite and synthetic diamonds, adsorbent carbon and graphitic fibers, glassy carbons, diamond-like carbon, etc. These are used nowadays for application in various forms like electrodes and electrical contacts, lubricants, shoe polish, gemstones, high performance tennis rackets, aircraft and spacecraft composites, heat sinks for ultrafast semiconductors, etc.[1]. By using hydrothermal method Graphite powder was prepared, the carbon source materials of graphite (flaky graphite), NaOH, Glucose we have synthesized fine nano rods of Graphite powder and its crystal size was calculated by using Scherer equation. Its value is equal to 72 nm and its predominant plane of (002) was confirmed by using the JCPDS file 75-1621 peaks were confirmed and well matched with the results. Band gap 5.38 eV value of the Graphite powder was analysed by UV-Vis Spectroscopy [2]. FTIR Spectrometer inferred that two main peaks located at about 963 -1474 cm⁻¹ and 2369-3464 cm⁻¹ which confirmed the formation of Graphite nanostructures. The FE-SEM and EDAX analysis demonstrate that the morphology changed from dense to fiber in hollow and hollow nano rods with increase the relative decreasing size of synthesized Graphite powder. Synthesized Graphite powder was used to study about the biological applications of antifungal activities of it [3].

Keywords; Graphite powder, Scherer equation, Glucose and FTIR

References

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